

MODELLING THE CONSOLIDATION OF PARTIALLY IMPREGNATED PREPREGS

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SUMMARY

A finite element model is developed to solve consolidation problems for composites manufacturing. The model is developed from a generic two-phase continuum theory allowing for coupling between the solid and fluid responses. The code is applied to a case study consisting of consolidation of a hat stringer to evaluate nonlinear effects.

Keywords: finite element model, two-phase continuum, engineered vacuum channel prepreg.

INTRODUCTION

The use of advanced composite materials is now increasing dramatically. Having previously been used predominately in low-volume high-cost production, such as spacecraft and military aircraft, composite materials are now being introduced on a large scale in commercial aircraft. The new Airbus A350 and Boeing 787 contain over 50% composites by weight, as compared to a only few percent in the previous generations.

Figure 1. Multiple simultaneous processes in an Engineered Vacuum Channels (EVaC) prepreg.

The necessary transition from slow manual manufacturing to more efficient automated processes implies that several process steps are performed simultaneously rather than sequentially. Previously, a typical sequence of operations would begin with a fully impregnated prepreg tape, stack the tape on a tool, then mould, then consolidate, and finally cure the component. Now the trend is to stack a flat tape lay-up, then mould,

impregnate and consolidate at the same time. To facilitate this multi-process the modern tapes and prepregs are manufactured with the so-called Engineered Vacuum Channels (EVaC) [1]. As a consequence we are faced with a set of processes occurring simultaneously, as illustrated in Figure 1.

The trouble is of course, that such complexity cannot be handled by current commercial process simulation software. Also, there are only relatively few multi-process models published in the open literature so far. There exist a few one-dimensional models that couple preform deformation and resin flow in the thickness direction of a laminate, as reviewed [2]. Unfortunately, the one-dimensional approach only applies to simple geometries with small curvature. Until recently, the only exception to this rule was the two-phase 2-D FEM-model in [2], used to simulate autoclave processes. The authors adapted an incremental, quasi-linear elastic model assuming infinitesimal strains. In consequence, Hubert et al. did not update the mesh geometry, permeability or fibre orientation during the course of process.

Recently, Li and Tucker [3] developed a far more advanced two-phase continuum based process model assuming hyperelasticity for the fibre network stress, which is valid for large deformations. The geometry was updated at each time step and accounted fully for the associated geometric nonlinearities. However, the work of Li and Tucker focus on traditional fully pre-impregnated prepregs and does not account for the simultaneous ply infiltration.

To attack this coupled problem, we have proposed a three-dimensional generic two-phase continuum mechanical framework [4], which allows modelling of multiple simultaneous and interacting sub-processes in a thermodynamically consistent manner. The model of Larsson et al. [4] was specialised in [5] to the consolidation of commingled yarn-based composites involving the following simultaneous sub processes: (I) forming into shape and (II) wetting and compaction of fibres bundles by the resin. This model is valid for large deformations and accounts fully for the associated geometric nonlinearities. However, it did not account for the seepage flow.

The specific objective of the present work is to model, simulate and demonstrate manufacturing operations of prepreg-based composites involving the following simultaneous subprocesses: (I) forming into shape and (II) wetting and compaction of fibres plies by the resin. This is an intermediate step before developing a fully integrated model for EVaC composites manufacturing that involves all the mentioned subprocesses; (I)-(III), c.f. Figure 1.

THEORETICAL AND NUMERICAL MODEL

In the following section an overview of the theoretical foundation for modelling of the deformation and consolidation and the resulting numerical methods are reviewed. Detailed theoretical descriptions of the model are given in references [4] and [5].

Constituents, Continuum Phases and Deformation Processes

The approach taken is to model composite consolidation adopting a two-phase continuum consideration of the three constituents, fibres, matrix and voids; where the

treatment of fibres and voids is simplified by associating them with one continuum phase, the solid phase. The matrix is represented by the second continuum phase, the liquid.

The solid and fluid phases are denoted s and f , respectively. Their volume fractions n^s and n^f are defined in terms of the constituents as:

$$n^s(\mathbf{x}, t) = \phi^p(\mathbf{x}, t) + \phi^v(\mathbf{x}, t) \text{ and } n^f(\mathbf{x}, t) = \phi^l(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (1)$$

where ϕ^p is the particle volume fraction, ϕ^v the void volume fraction and ϕ^l the liquid volume fraction. The intrinsic density, associated with each phase, is denoted ρ^α , where $\alpha = s, f$.

During forming of the considered material system, at least four primary modes of deformation can be identified. These are the two processes at the meso-scale due to inter-ply deformation (pregreg deformations and seepage flow) and the two processes at the micro-scale due to intra-ply deformation (ply deformations and infiltration flow). It is assumed that the meso-scale processes are governed by the macroscopic tractions and deformations. The micro-scale processes, on the other hand, are assumed to be governed by the fluid pressure and ply compaction, cf. Figure 1.

Two-Phase Continuum

Following the development in [4,5], it is assumed that each spatial point of the mixture is simultaneously occupied by particles from the solid and fluid phase. Upon deformation the continuum phases move via individual non-linear deformation maps, φ^s and φ^f , defined as

$$\mathbf{x} = \boldsymbol{\varphi}^\alpha(\mathbf{X}^\alpha, t), \quad \alpha = s, f, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{x} denotes the current position of a continuum particle \mathbf{X}^α at the time t .

Figure 2. Deformations of a two-phase continua.

The localised form of the entropy inequality for the mixture is specified in [4] as

$$\mathcal{D} = \dot{\bar{s}} + \rho^f \mathbf{v}^d \cdot \nabla_{S^f} \geq 0. \quad (3)$$

Moreover, by introducing entropy production in terms of internal energy and Helmholtz free energy, ψ , the equation (3) transforms to

$$\mathcal{D} = \dot{\bar{e}} - \dot{\bar{\psi}} + \rho^f \mathbf{v}^d \cdot \nabla s^f \geq 0. \quad (4)$$

Finally, upon combining (4) with momentum, mass and energy balance equations, the entropy inequality for the solid-fluid interaction is obtained as

$$\mathcal{D} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbf{l} - n^s p \dot{\varepsilon} - \hat{\rho}^s \dot{\psi} - \mathbf{h}_e^f \cdot \mathbf{v}^d \geq 0, \quad (5)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} + p \mathbf{1}$ is the Terzaghi effective stress, $\mathbf{h}_e^f = \nabla p - \rho^f \mathbf{g}$ is the effective drag force, $\mathbf{l} = \mathbf{v} \otimes \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} = \dot{\mathbf{F}} \cdot \mathbf{F}^{-1}$ is the spatial velocity gradient, $\mathbf{F} = \boldsymbol{\varphi} \otimes \nabla_{\mathbf{x}}$ is the deformation gradient, $\mathbf{v}^d := n^s (\mathbf{v}^f - \mathbf{v}^s)$ is the Darcian velocity and ε is the logarithmic volumetric strain in the solid phase defined as

$$\varepsilon = -\ln \frac{\rho^s}{\rho_0^s}. \quad (6)$$

Constitutive Models

For simplicity, it is assumed that there is no coupling on the constitutive level between the fibre network deformations in terms of the right Cauchy-Green deformation tensor, \mathbf{C} , and the intrinsic compaction, ε . Moreover, the intrinsic compaction due to matrix infiltration is represented as an internal variable denoted, ε^p , and the free energy is assumed to possess the additive structure

$$\psi = \psi(\mathbf{C}, \varepsilon, \varepsilon^p) = \psi^1(\mathbf{C}) + \psi^2(\varepsilon, \varepsilon^p). \quad (7)$$

The constitutive equations are established by distinguishing three different types of dissipative mechanism of the total dissipation defined as

$$\mathcal{D} = \underbrace{\boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbf{l}}_{\mathcal{D}_1} - \underbrace{n^s p \dot{\varepsilon}}_{\mathcal{D}_2} - \underbrace{\hat{\rho}^s \dot{\psi}}_{\mathcal{D}_3} - \mathbf{h}_e^f \cdot \mathbf{v}^d \geq 0, \quad (8)$$

where the dissipative mechanism \mathcal{D}_1 , is due to effective stress response, \mathcal{D}_2 is due to fluid pressure, and \mathcal{D}_3 due to macroscopic Darcy flow. Note, that these mechanisms correspond to the material responses of (i) elastic interaction between plies, (ii) wetting and compressing of fibre plies by the liquid resin and (iii) macroscopic matrix flow between and within plies, i.e. macroscopic seepage. Full theoretical descriptions of \mathcal{D}_1 and \mathcal{D}_2 are given in reference [5], whereas a theoretical model for \mathcal{D}_3 is found in the paper by Larsson and Larsson [4].

Boundary Value Problem

The FE-model is developed considering composite manufacturing using no-bleeding EVaC-prepreg in an autoclave process. In the studied process, the components are usually subjected to an external uniform pressure sufficient to drive the infiltration of

resin into the plies. However, the overall pressure gradients are too weak to drive any significant macroscopic Darcy flow in the no-bleeding prepreg. Therefore, it is assumed that $\mathcal{D}_3 \equiv 0$. Thus, the subsequent development is specialised to the undrained condition.

In the finite element solution the weak form of the momentum balance for the mixture of solid and fluid phases, written in terms of the balance between internal virtual work G^{int} and external virtual work G^{ext} is considered. In order to solve the non-linear governing equations, the weak form of the internal virtual work is linearised with respect to virtual velocity and discretised using finite element. For details see references [4,5]. The final implementation is both in an in-house FE software and as a user subroutine in the commercial FE software ANSYS [6].

EXPERIMENTAL

The partially impregnated prepreg used in this study was HexPly® M21 T700 consisting of 57 % by volume of carbon fibres and 43 % epoxy resin. Prior to testing, the inner structure of the prepreg was characterised by fracturing samples under cryogenic condition. The surface of fracture was then examined and photographed using both optical and sweep electron microscope.

The testing apparatus used to measure the compaction response is described in detail elsewhere [7]. Using this apparatus, a cross-laminate specimen $[0/90/0/90]_s$ was compressed out of plane (the main deformation mode of a fibre bed) at a temperature of 120°C, i.e. well above melt temperature of the considered epoxy. To evaluate the preform response in isolation, the tool was closed at increasing levels of displacement and the resin pressure allowed relax, due to the assumed combination of macroscopic seepage and microscopic infiltration. This approach is motivated by considering the total Cauchy stress of the mixture, $\bar{\sigma} = \sigma^s + \sigma^f$, and observing that the stress carried by the preform is the solid stress σ^s as $\sigma^f \rightarrow 0$.

The procedure to characterise the fibre bed compaction consists of deforming the specimen to increasing levels of displacement, as described in [8,7]. At each increment, the displacement is held constant until the load relaxes to a stable value. Assuming the composite material as a simple viscoelastic system, the value of the relaxed load will correspond to the elastic response of the material, which is the fibre bed effective stress for a given strain. By loading the specimen to different displacement levels, the complete fibre bed compaction response is extracted from the displacements and the relaxed load values at each loading step. From the master curve, the relaxed load is plotted against the displacement at each holding step. Since the rate of relaxation is not known a priori, the relaxation was allowed for two different time scales separated by nearly one decade.

A total of six cross-ply $[0/90/0/90]_s$ \varnothing 120 mm specimens were prepared by laying-up 8 plies of HexPly® M21 T carbon–epoxy prepregs. The specimens were then tested in a servo-hydraulic testing machine; Instron 8501. The testing conditions, namely the temperature, were selected to minimize the viscosity of the resin and to maximize the duration of the test before the resin starts to cure. With these conditions, the test duration was maximally 150 min, which does not allow the resin to cure significantly.

RESULTS

Figure 3. Typical sections through the M21 prepreg showing the partially impregnated plies

The typical section through M21 prepreg is illustrated by the micrographs in Figure 3. Figure 3a and b, shows an overview of the unconsolidated material. Figure 3c and d, shows a close-up view of the inner structure of the unconsolidated material. Here we notice that the inner parts of the ply are dry. Finally, a microscopic study of the samples revealed a fairly constant size of the dry zone and a resulting length to infiltrate of approximately $\zeta = 50 \mu\text{m}$.

The data from the relaxation experiments were used to obtain the relationship between the stress and the fibre volume fraction, see Figure 4. To calculate the model parameters, the elastic limit (the end of each relaxation event) was found for each step; see Figure 4, and the data fitted to the constitutive model from reference [5]. During the experiments, it was observed that squeeze flow occurred at fibre volume fraction of approximately 70 %. Therefore, the only the response between 40 and 65 % was used for parameter identification. The resulting parameters are $kE = k^s E = 2.3 \text{ GPa}$ and $m = \beta = 19.1$ for the short relaxation times and $kE = k^s E = 5.1 \text{ GPa}$ and $m = \beta = 19.6$ for the long relaxation times, cf. reference [4].

Figure 4. Stress vs. fibre volume fraction for the two cases: short and long relaxation times. Also in the figure; the elastic limit is indicated.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

In the following example the developed methodology is used for process modelling of a hat stringer. The preform is assumed to be of a quasi-isotropic layup. The implemented constitutive model is based on the material data given by the manufacturer and the consolidation experiments. The model parameters are summarised in Table 1. Intra-ply permeability was computed using the model for unidirectional reinforcement by Gebart [9].

Table 1. The material parameters for the M21 T700 material

Param	E [GPa]	$k=k^s$	$m=\beta$	ϕ_0	ζ [μm]	μ [Pa/s]	G [GPa]
Value	230	0.0174	19.1	0.685	50	50	8.8

In general the material parameters for the present model consist of the parameter vector: $\kappa = \{kE, k^s E, m, \beta, \phi_0, \Upsilon(\mu, \zeta, K(r))\}$, where E is the Young modulus of the fibres, k and k^s are pre-exponential factors, m and β are exponents, ϕ_0 is initial volume fraction, Υ is the effective drag, μ is resin viscosity at 120°C, ζ is infiltration length, K is permeability, and the radius of the fibres is approximately 7 μm . Moreover, the parameter ϕ_0 may be calculated using nominal volume fractions ϕ_∞^p via the relation

$$\phi_\infty^p = \frac{\phi_0^p}{1 - \phi_0^v} \quad (9)$$

together with the saturation conditions, and definitions of the local volume fraction. For the initial void volume fraction, we used the value $\phi^v \approx 5\%$, even if it is not supported by the micrographs. Finally, stiffness parameters $k^s E$, kE and exponents m and β , are taken as a mean value for both the long and short relaxation times.

Figure 5. Assessment of the model response against experimental data for sample 1.

Figure 6. The finite element model and applied boundary conditions; displacement constrains displayed in blue and pressures displayed in red.

The fitted model parameter were used to simulate the perform consolidation, as shown in Figure 5. The model response is compared there against the experimental data for sample 1. The comparison is performed for a single load step only. However, the model response will asymptotically approach the elastic limit if multiple steps are modelled. Using the literature data, the estimated wetting length and the fitted kE , $k^s E$ and m , β value the model gives reasonable agreement with experiments, cf. Figure 6. However, the model seems to slightly overestimate the wetting rate.

In the numerical example, finite-element analysis of undrained consolidation of a composites hat stringer, as shown in Figure 6, is considered. Consolidation pressure of 8 bar is applied on the inner surface of the stringer. In order to emulate the loading on the stringer, the pressure is applied during a time period of 1 second and kept constant at the nominal level afterwards for 100 seconds. The outer boundary, in accordance with

the real case, is constrained in all degrees of freedom. Due to symmetry, only one half of the stringer is modelled. The elements used in the analysis are ANSYS bilinear enhanced quads: PLANE182.

Figure 7. Degree of infiltration after 100 seconds.

Figure 7 shows snapshots of the infiltration taken after 100 second for consolidation. It is noticed that the degree of infiltration is almost homogenous at around 45 %. However, the inner corner exhibits slightly lower degree of infiltration than the outer corner. The reason for that is realised by taking the equilibrium at any of the corner. For instance, considering the outer corner indicates a higher total pressure at the tool-side than on the bag side of the laminate, since the arc length is larger there. The opposite, of course, arises at the inner corner. This local increase in the total pressure is believed to cause resin migration and corner thinning at the outer corner and corner thickening at the inner corner.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The main contribution of the present work is the application of existing models to consolidation of EVaC preregs. Furthermore, the present approach rests on the general two-phase continuum theory, thus providing a framework for modelling interactions between different physical processes. Using this framework, the existing model has been adapted to the autoclave process and the parameters fitted using experiments and data from open literature. The constitutive models are finally implemented into a finite element code ANSYS for modelling of pressure driven consolidation of a hat stringer.

In the present development we assumed that the pressure gradients are small enough that any macroscopic Darcy flow may be neglected. However, the corner effects in Figure 7 generate pressure gradients. Therefore, an accurate analysis of a hat stringer should include the macroscopic Darcy flow. The continuum framework already includes

the term \mathcal{D}_{III} , which defines the macroscopic Darcy flow. Introducing the macroscopic Darcy flow is thus a natural next step in this development.

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References

1. S. Thomas , C. Bongiovanni, S.R. Nutt, In situ estimation of through-thickness resin flow using ultrasound, *Composites Science and Technology*, 2008, 68:3093–3098
2. P. Hubert, R. Vaziri and A. Poursartip, A two-dimensional flow model for the process simulation of complex shape composite laminates. *International Journal of Numerical Methods in Engineering* 1999, 44:1–26.
3. M. Li, C.L. Tucker, Modelling and Simulation of Two-Dimensional Consolidation for Thermoset Matrix Composites, *Composites; Part A* 2002; 33:877-892.
4. R. Larsson, M. Wysocki, S. Toll, Process-modelling of composites using two-phase porous media theory, *European Journal of Mechanics A/Solids* 2004; 23:15-36.
5. M. Wysocki, Continuum modelling of composites consolidation, PhD thesis ISBN/ISSN 91-7291-874-8 at Chalmers University of Technology 2006, Department of Applied Mechanics.
6. M. Wysocki, ANSYS implementation for modelling the consolidation of commingled composites, SICOMP Report TN06-006, 2006
7. M. Wysocki, B. Nyström, Modelling the consolidation of partially impregnated Prepregs, SICOMP Report CR09-021, 2009
8. P. Hubert, A. Poursartip, A method for the direct measurement of the fibre bed compaction curve of composite prepregs, *Composites: Part A*, 2001, 32:179–187
9. B.R. Gebart, Permeability of Unidirectional Reinforcement for RTM, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1992, 26:1100-1133